

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

Deployment of profiling floats as pairs

Deliverable D1.5

**Funded by
the European Union**

**UK Research
and Innovation**

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

<https://ocean-ice.eu/>

About this document

Deliverable: D1.5 Deployment of profiling floats as pairs

Work Package: WP1 Subpolar circulation, heat delivery and water mass export

Delivery date: 23 April 2026

Type of document: Report

Dissemination level: Public

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Cover sheet: Photo of an ARVOR-I float profiler (next to other assets) being testing in front of Thwaites ice shelf in West Antarctica before deployment in the Amundsen Sea. Photo Credit: Pierre Dutrieux.

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1. Publishable summary

In this deliverable, we present an overview of profiler deployments in Antarctic Shelf Seas organised by the OCEAN ICE project and provide access to the data, which is quality controlled and being gathered and served to the general public in near-real time and following FAIR principles through internet interfaces such as EURO-ARGO (<https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu>).

The OCEAN ICE project deployed upwards of 16 profilers in Antarctic shelf seas to date, using seabed parking mode between profiles to minimize drift and increase odds of staying within areas where sea ice melts away seasonally. This operational mode provides access to satellite communication, data gathering and eventual reconfiguration of individual profiler parameters every austral Summer.

Fig. 1: Location of deployments of profilers deployed by OCEAN ICE associated countries since 2023 South of 45S (large circles) overlaid on world map. Red rectangles indicate areas where OCEAN ICE deployments occurred. Since 2023, international collaborators and OCEAN ICE investigators have deployed more profilers in Antarctic shelf seas using other sources of funding.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

The OCEANICE project, under WP1 and WP10, deployed 16 Float profilers to date from five different campaigns (see Table 1). These observations have been integrated within and are maintained and curated by the ARGO programme, Euro-ARGO in the European Union. This includes the integration of six profilers deployed by OCEAN ICE Ukrainian collaborators under WP10, which are curated by Euro-ARGO at the Coriolis data centre.

Unlike classical ARGO profilers which aim at drifting at a parking depth of 1000m between profiles and satellite communication sequences, OCEAN ICE profilers follow a dedicated seabed parking mode programme aimed at minimizing overall drifting. Our goal is to avoid drifting in regions permanently covered by either sea or glacier ice which would prevent surfacing and data gathering. Thanks to the OCEAN ICE and other programmes, the ARGO community is starting to obtain sufficient numbers of test cases in various shelf seas settings to be able to quantify the validity of this approach to sample remote and treacherous polar regions.

2.2 Achievements

After 2 years of operation, as of April 2026, out of the 16 profilers deployed, 11 are still active, giving a survival rate approaching 70% in polar seas. Furthermore, the capability of profilers to sample across full seasonal and interannual timescales and cover the entire water column is unique in polar seas, as other timeseries record are moored and more discrete and limited in the vertical, especially near the surface where icebergs prevent installation of mooring lines.

To date, the 16 OCEAN ICE profilers provided 1016 profiles in Antarctic shelf seas (1116 for all profilers noted in Table 1), with sensor accuracy approaching state of the art ship-based approach. Assuming profiler cost of 20.000€, and negligible telemetry costs, these profiles were obtained at a cost of 320.000€. Conservatively assuming daily cost for a Research Vessel Icebreaker of number of 50.000€, and 2-hour time needed to do a ship-based cast to 2000m depth, obtaining the same number of profiles using ship-based means would have costed above 4.2Million Euro. We note here that the comparison is somewhat dubious, as the means available to a large research vessel are not comparable to float profilers, inversely vessels would not be able to operate in the settings where profiler function during austral Winter, etc. Nevertheless, this comparison provides an idea of the benefit provided by this technology.

2.3 Open Science

Datasets

The data underlying this deliverable are deposited in near real time through the ARGO programme data centers, and served to all on open access platform managed by the Euro-ARGO programme, e.g. <https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu>

A more detailed view of all individual assets deployed during OCEAN ICE and follow up programmes is displayed in table 1 (WMO numbers contain hyperlink to the data), with access to individual profiler data at: <https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/#WMOofProfilerBelow>

FLOAT PROFILER details

PROGRAMME	PROJECT	SERIAL NUMBER	DEPLOY. DATE	LAT	LON	Ship	Cruise #	WMO
Argo UK	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-25UK001	Jan-26	-74.90	-102.34	RVIB Araon	ANA16B	2901937
Argo UK	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-25UK002	Jan-26	-73.81	-106.55	RVIB Araon	ANA16B	2901938
Argo BSH	Argo BSH	AI2600-24DE023	Mar-25	-64.51	99.38	Nuyina	Denman	7902220
Argo BSH	Argo BSH	AI2600-24DE022	Mar-25	-65.37	99.10	Nuyina	Denman	2903934
Argo UK	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-23UK001	Jan-24	-74.89	-102.33	RVIB Araon	ANA14B	1902687
Argo UK	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-23UK002	Jan-24	-74.34	-104.91	RVIB Araon	ANA14B	5907093
Argo UK	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-23UK003	Jan-24	-78.28	-173.82	RV Laura Bassi		3902582
Argo UK	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-23UK004	Jan-24	-74.05	-112.48	RVIB Araon	ANA14B	4903786
AWI	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-23DE104	Jan-24	-67.23	80.54	Polarstern	PS140	4903780
AWI	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-23DE102	Jan-24	-68.58	73.18	Polarstern	PS140	5907087
AWI	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-23DE101	Jan-24	-68.00	70.94	Polarstern	PS140	6990621
AWI	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-23DE103	Jan-24	-68.92	77.32	Polarstern	PS140	6990622
Ukraine	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-25UA003	Mar-25	-63.50	-61.53	Noosfera		3902667
Ukraine	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-25UA002	Mar-25	-63.61	-61.96	Noosfera		4903872
Ukraine	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-25UA001	Mar-25	-63.61	-62.14	Noosfera		7902285
Ukraine	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-25UA005	Mar-25	-63.54	-60.55	Noosfera		2903996
Ukraine	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-25UA006	Mar-25	-63.29	-60.01	Noosfera		7902290
Ukraine	OCEAN ICE	AI2600-25UA004	Mar-25	-63.56	-60.98	Noosfera		5907175

Table 1: Location and time of deployments of profilers under the OCEAN ICE and follow up partner programmes led by OCEAN ICE investigators.

3. Results

Following on the successes of OCEAN ICE deployments and data gathering, other projects and programmes are now building up to deploy more profilers in polar shelf seas. The example of ARGO BSH is given in table

1, but there are many others, funded through various sources. We are therefore confident that the methodology and approach developed and improved through OCEAN ICE will have a long-lasting legacy.

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the following project objectives, as described in the action description.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica, particularly relating to ice sheet-ocean interaction and deep water formation and export.

This dataset samples regions and temporal windows in the seasonal cycle that have never been observed before, so significantly reduces spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations.

O2: Improve critical ice sheet-ocean processes in numerical models, using historical observations and new data sets obtained in the project.

This dataset feeds WP7 and aims at providing evaluation means and boundary conditions for numerical modeling efforts within OCEAN ICE and beyond.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

All observations are available after quality control and following fair principles through ARGO and national data servers.

O9: Fill in the existing “hole” in the quasi-circumpolar OCEAN-ICE analysis of shelf transport and exchange with the contribution of Ukrainian purchased and deployed profiling floats.

These observations constrain the oceanic controls on heat and freshwater delivery to and from ‘cold’ (e.g. Weddell Sea) as well as ‘warm’ (Amundsen Sea) sites of ice sheet-ocean interaction around Antarctica, and the processes operating in these regions.